

RELIGION AND ITS LANGUAGE USAGE IN ORAL DISCOURSE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5917800>

ABSTRACT: Religion is a set of beliefs of an individual or a group of people. Religion has got a firm place in people's life of all the time and its language is as holy and sacred as any religion itself. Religion Language is prior and at the same time distinctive to everyday language of every nation. Regarding its function, style and interrelation with other contexts, religion language is quite dynamic and complex. In this article, we tried to analyze, firstly, religion itself and given definition along with terms related to language of religion. The importance of using religion based language and phrases in everyday discourse of people is also studied.

Keywords: *religion, discourse, context, truth, God, belief, sect, secular, sacred.*

The complex results of certain studies done on topic of religion show that, appearance of religion links to the human birth in this universe. According to the religion claims, Religions surely came along with Adam. For the first step of analysis, we provide some definitions of the term "religion": thus, "The belief and worship of a superhuman controlling power, especially a personal God or gods"¹. According to Britannica Concise Encyclopedia, religion is the relation of people to their own God or the gods or to whatever they consider sacred or, in some cases, merely supernatural.

One of the linguistic scientists of the department of English at University of Sargodha, Hasan Naeem claims that, an organized collection of beliefs, cultural systems and world views that relate to an order of existence is called religion.

All religions have such elements:

Belief- a sense of brain and it belongs to faith for no reason. Examples: belief in God, Death, Heaven, Hell;

Ritual – ceremonial practices observed in all religion types. Examples: Christmas, Holi, Eids;

Emotions- emotions of hope, fear, respect;

Organization- religion is well organized with belief, emotions and rituals, without organization a religion cannot survive;

Sect- every religion has tiny set of people who follow differing from the main religion called sect. Examples: Islam has: Shia & Sunni, Christianity has: Catholics & Protestants.

Religions complete the psychic needs of a human being and maintains social solidarity in his or her group of life. Fear and anxiety is removed by religion. Religion is considered to the protector of values and make individuals be a main part of their society. Religion has got a firm role not only in psychic needs of people but also it plays a great role in a language of the society where it is followed by.

In 2014 on September 11, there was a research done on Americans to find out who are highly religious and who less religious. Here is the table:

Table 1.

Profile of “highly religious” respondents

	Highly religious %	Not highly religious %
Religion very important	91	31
Religion less important	9	69
Believing in God	96	57
Praying Regularly	88	35
Reading Bible/ other materials	70	18
Catholic	17	21
Don't know/ refused	-	1

In this report, “highly religious” respondents are inferred as those who say they pray daily.

According to Hasan Naeem, Language of Religion is a register that represents the variations of language, used in the setup of religion, from the everyday language and other setups.² Of course, religion language is totally different from every day language, it has got some aspects that usual language has not. In other words language of religion is prior to everyday language.

The standard of the contemporary language is religious language. There certain books reflecting some religions, such as, The Holy Quran and Bible. The Holy Quran is written in Arabic language and because of this unique style, it is considered to be the standard of Arabic. In addition to this, another holy book is

²Language of Religion//Hasan Naeem//1 Jul, 2014, pp 40.

Bible and it is consisted of some standards of a language and full of figurative language. A significant relation among people is set up by language and religion. The interplay between language and religion is so obvious and we cannot ignore it. Thus, we can consider religion to be quite extensively influential in a community as it can effect all parts and aspects of a society ranging from education, science, architecture to ethics and behavior. “ For many people all over the world religion is indispensable, without which they cannot continue their lives and existences”³

Now we turn to the other type of discussion and talk about religion related words in every day discourse of people. Occasionally, we find ourselves in a conversation with a friend who is not in our sect or religion. And, in this condition one should pay close attention when their talk turns to things related to religion. For example, the Islamic world and the Christianity are differ from each other. Let us look some words related to a religion content and have already become an essential part of people’s communication:

1. Bless, blessed, blessing- it is origin comes from the English word *blood*, as in consecration through sacrifice. We regularly, hear someone is saying, “Bless you” or “ God bless you”. The word means different meaning in different contexts, such as: “happiness” or “to please”.
2. Sin, sinful, sinners- this word also highly used by every religion followers (Muslims, Christians, and non- Christians) and its being an empty term. People easily talk when they are about their “sins” and “mistakes” and say “I just messed up”. Our sins are against our God and other people.
3. Holy, holiness- the idea of “moral purity” is intended by this term.
4. Glory, glorify- this term is commonly known through Bible and some western music. And this term bears the meaning of “ to be heavy”.
5. Secular- not concerned with or devoted to religion.
6. Faithful - in terms of religion, this word means, a group of people who adhere to a common faith and habitually attend a given church.
7. Tolerance- commonly used term; the act of tolerating something; a permissible difference.
8. Misbelieve – holding a false or unorthodox belief.

Thus, above stated words are commonly seen or heard in our daily life. And now let us to clarify some idioms related to religion with their meanings:

1. *An act of God*: is something such as an earthquake or floods that human beings cannot control;

³Language and Religion; Linguistic Religion or Religious Language by Ali Rahimi, June2011, pp1.

2. *Heaven knows*: used when somebody does not feel recognized or appreciated. For example: “Heaven knows how I work to make my family happy”.
3. *A man of God*: is a clergyman.

So, it can be concluded that, religion and its language is an essential part of our lives. Religion itself and language of religion is prior to people’s oral discourse, however, it is very hard to imagine the communication between them without having religion related terms.

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